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Diplomacy of Good Neighbourliness in Inter-State Relations: A Study of the Roles of Neighbouring Countries in the Nigerian Civil War 1967 – 1970

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Abstract

Good neighbourliness as it relates to foreign policy has an imperativeness of its own, only for the fact that the use of force, the ultimate alternative, is uneconomical, no matter the means and might. In its bare essentials, good neighbourliness cannot be assumed or its potential taken for granted. It has to be created, consciously coveted, and facilitated to balance gains and losses. Mankind grapples with problems such as urbanisation, globalisation, population explosion, terrorism, insurgency, and climate change, among others. Given that these problematic issues are and will continue to remain with man as a reference point in the future, the ontological dynamics of good neighbourliness in international relations remain a sine-qua-non. The world has become a global village, and the foreign policy of a nation must align with this stark reality. Nigeria's foreign policy from inception has been African-centred and concentrically operated, meaning that Nigeria positively aligns itself with nations of African descent, the closest of which would be its immediate neighbours. This positive disposition, especially towards its immediate neighbours, is a derivative of African traditional social values, and it is within this ambience that Nigeria's external relations are anchored. The experience of Nigeria during the period of its civil strife demonstrates as much. This paper is therefore, a study of the relevance of good neighbourliness with reference to Nigeria and her immediate neighbours during the civil war years. It is an exposition to bring to the fore the impact of Nigeria's brotherly disposition towards its immediate neighbours and their contributions to the resolution of its civil crisis. Using a historical analysis methodology, the paper submits that good neighbourliness, which invokes the spirit of filial familiarity and harmony, is a necessity both in domestic and international relations, provided it strikes a balance between gains and losses within the ambit of national interest.

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Introduction

Conceptually, good neighbourliness is derived from the sociology of family into the vocabulary of foreign relations. It invokes the spirit of filial familiarity and harmony common to the most coherent of all the social units—the family to that of foreign relations—a category of human activity in which the interesting units, state actors, are not least coherent and inherently sharply divided that they are bound to disharmony than harmony¹. Nigeria's good neighbourly disposition is a product of historical affinity derived from disingenuously drawn boundaries². It is the territorial hegemony that the same colonial history has bestowed on Nigeria that created Cameroun in the East, Chad in the North East, Niger in the North, Benin in the West, and Equatorial Guinea just off the coast of the South South. With these immediate neighbours, Nigeria has maintained good neighbourly relations as an article of faith, though in practice, it has really been a “blow hot, blow cold fair.” In short, Nigeria's good neighbourly relations with its immediate neighbours was interpreted and acted upon on a free-choice basis, respectively, with fluctuating outcomes.³

Of all the developments that took place in post-independence Nigeria, specifically in the first ten years (1960–1971), perhaps the most important and enduring was the thirty-month civil war that commenced in 1967 and ended in 1970. The survival and emergence of Nigeria as one indivisible entity out of the ravages of that fratricidal war marked a watershed in the country's political development. However, for Nigeria to have survived the war, it must have been the result of various contributory factors within the domestic and external realms. Within the external domain, one important factor stands out that contributed immensely to the maintenance of Nigeria's territorial integrity: the roles played by its immediate neighbours in the civil war, and by extension, the support and assistance from Benin, Chad, Cameroun, Equatorial Guinea, and Niger Republic to Nigeria during its civil war.

This paper is an attempt to examine the roles played by Nigeria's immediate neighbouring countries during the thirty-month civil war. To understand what informed their staunch support for Nigeria, this paper analysed some historical developments that influenced the attitudes of these five African countries towards Nigeria during the war and post-civil war foreign policy towards them.

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Nigeria and Its immediate Neighbours before Independence

Before the Berlin Conference of 1884–45 and the subsequent partition of Africa by European powers, quite a number of ethnic nationalities were incorporated into the French colonial territories, such as the Yoruba in Dahomey (Benin), the Hausa in Niger, the Shuwa Kanuri and Serer in Chad, the Mandara, Gude, Fulani, and Matakam in Cameroun, and were subjects of the rulers of several kingdoms and empires in the Nigerian area, notably the Sokoto Caliphate, Bornu Empire, and Oyo Kingdom. The physical separation of the various ethnic groups by the colonial powers did not bring an end to their economic, social, cultural, and even spiritual links. Migration, both in and out of the Nigerian area, had been taking place for many years up to the colonial period.⁵

During the colonial period, people cultivated their farms, which were located on the opposite sides of the border. The near impossibility of policing the frontiers simply meant that the members of the divided clans and ethnic nations continued to maintain their links, passing to and fro across the frontiers at will. Despite decades of administrative, political, educational, and ideological divides, Africans continued to maintain social relations. At a critical moment in the civil war, when President Hammani attended one of the several peace meetings, he is reported to have said that while he sympathised with the plight of the critical mass of Biafra, if Niger made any overt move towards recognition of the rebels, his people would not allow him back in the country.⁶

Colonel Alley of Dahomey (Benin) faced a similar pressure from the Yorubas. Also, there is every reason to believe that President Ahmadu Ahidjo's enthusiastic support for the Nigerian government throughout the period of the civil war derived partially from the sentimental pressure of his Fulani subjects.⁷ Nigeria's link with its immediate neighbouring countries during the colonial period, which influenced their behaviour during the Nigerian crisis, however, went beyond primordial relations. The networks of administrative, political, economic, educational, and socio-cultural aspects of relationships that Nigeria established with the neighbouring countries were strengthened through deliberate policies, especially in the first few years of independence.

Administratively, all former British colonies in West Africa (Nigeria, Ghana, Sierra Leone, and the Gambia) were made to share common institutions and services, such as the West African Currency Board, among others. Similarly, the merging of

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Southern Cameroun with Nigeria in 1922 and the enormous amount of money spent by the Nigerian government on the administration and other services of the trusteeship territory went a long way in the establishment and maintenance of cordial relations between the peoples of these two territories. These cordial relations were further enhanced by the fact that quite a number of Cameroun educated elites received their higher education in Nigerian institutions.⁸ Their association with Nigeria and intimacy with its domestic politics accounted for their sympathetic understanding in which they viewed the Nigerian crisis.

Colonial tie-ups, administrative associations, hash colonial policies in French territories, and the search for economic opportunities encouraged large scale movements of people throughout West Africa and beyond. The establishment of colonial administrative structures and institutions called for the spread of skilled labour and western education personnel from one part of British West Africa to another. They could therefore move and settle in any British colony without any hindrance. Nigeria's administrative, economic, and socio-cultural links with Southern Cameroun also resulted in a large influx of Nigerians into that territory. This was accelerated by the post-war expansion of the plantation industry in the territory. By 1954, about 25,000 men were employed on the Victoria plantation, and 6,000 were employed in the Kumba division. The need to meet the requirements, including food for the workers, encouraged more Nigerians to engage in trading activities with Cameroun. This influence exercised by Nigerians in this area constituted a major campaign issue when southern Cameroun had to choose between integration with Nigeria or unification with French Cameroun. The Cameroonians continued to appreciate the roles played by the Nigerian government in the development of their territory.⁹

Employment opportunities on plantations also led to large-scale migrations of Nigerians, largely of Eastern Nigerian origin, to Fernando Po. Here, migrations from Eastern Nigeria far outnumbered the indigenous population. Initially, the movement of Nigerians in and out of that island was coordinated and regulated by the two colonial powers, Britain and Spain, who controlled these territories. Recruitment of Nigerians as indentured labour for the Spanish plantation started around the 1940s. Depots for recruitment were opened at Afikpo and other places and were manned by Spaniards. Modes of recruitment, registration, transportation, issuance of travel documents, and

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conditions of service were agreed upon by Britain and Spain.¹⁰ As was the case with Southern Cameroun, the large number of Nigerians that migrated to Fernando Po led to the development of several industries, such as canoe and boat making, as well as intensive trading activities. Annual sports, which were organised between Fernando Po and the Nigerian Eastern Region, were financed by the Spaniards. This link, which continued in post-independence, played an important role in shaping the opinions of the Spaniards and later the Equatorial Guineans on the Nigerian civil war.

The movement of people across the border was not confined to these territories alone. In addition to these migrations, there were also long-distance movements of people from French-controlled territories such as Chad, Niger, etc. into Nigeria and vice versa. The harsh French colonial policies, especially on taxation, the occasional occurrence of drought, and the availability of employment opportunities in building construction and other areas of trade, led to the influx of people from Niger and Chad into Nigeria. On the other hand, a small number of Nigerians also settled in the French territories, notably in Chad, either on a temporary or permanent basis. They were engaged mainly in trading and other economic activities.¹¹

Nigeria's brisk trading relations with those territories throughout the colonial period have already been mentioned. However, it must be stressed that these, more than other factors, bound Nigeria more closely to its neighbours and beyond. Trading, which linked the different peoples of West Africa for centuries, survived the divisive policies of the colonial powers. It was in this respect, more than any other, that the colonial boundaries were rendered ineffective while trading activities between these territories were conducted freely. This notwithstanding, the goods that were carried across the borders were substantial, and their direction shifted to changing market situations.

In the early 1940s, Magariya (Niger) lost a large percentage of its groundnut crop to the border market in Nigeria. In the 1950s, there were frequent changes in both size and direction of the cross-border movement, with the direction of flow occasionally changing within mid-season. In 1951, about 60,000 tonnes of groundnut crossed the Nigerian border to Niger as a result of the increased value of groundnut in Niamey.¹² It would appear that about 10,000 tonnes of groundnut in Magariya (Niger) originated in Nigeria. Trading in other commodities like livestock, for which Nigeria, Chad, and Cameroun have been famous; grains, which were needed in the dry Sahel region; and

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other goods originating from Britain and France, were equally important. As in the pre-colonial period, these made the economies of the trading regions complementary. Such trading activities were also taking place between Nigeria and Dahomey (Benin).¹³

It is therefore clear that the pre-colonial linkages between the different peoples of West and Central Africa were maintained through the colonial period. This was in spite of the attempts by the colonial powers to discourage inter-African trade in order to satisfy their economic objectives by disorienting the directions of the trade to North-South as opposed to the East-West directions of the pre-colonial period. The elites of the various territories were quite aware of the importance of the maintenance of close economic and other links for their survival. The fragmented territories that experienced the difficulty of balancing their budgets were also aware of the significance of relating to a viable and helpful neighbour, and most of them looked up to Nigeria, especially for their economic survival. Some of the countries were afraid of the consequences of Nigeria's disintegration. For political reasons, even those countries that did not share common borders with Nigeria were aware of the role that Nigeria could play for their survival and as a leading black nation in the world.

Nigeria was indeed fully aware of its interests and responsibilities towards those countries. Partly as a result of its enlightened self-interest and partly due to its leader's perception of the hostility towards them and other African states by Nkrumah of Ghana. Nigeria's foreign policy from 1960 to 1966 was largely an attempt to isolate Nkrumah, neutralise the excessive influence of France on its former colonial territories in West Africa, and win the friendship and loyalty of its neighbours and other African states. This diplomatic posture paid off during the civil war.¹⁴

Nigeria and Its Immediate Neighbors between 1960 and 1966

To appreciate the reactions of Nigeria's neighbours to its civil conflict, it is necessary to examine Nigeria's diplomatic posture towards these countries between 1960 and 1966. Diplomacy, after all, is a cumulative process, and Nigeria's behaviour in the period preceding its civil war greatly influenced the reactions of its immediate neighbours and other state actors in Africa and the world at large. Nigeria's internal politics and its consciousness about its potential economic wealth and political influence in Africa and the world at large made the leadership to fashion out a functional foreign policy. Given the fragility of Nigeria's federal structure in the early years of independence, Nigeria's

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leaders were anxious that the surrounding international environment in West Africa should be conducive to domestic tranquillity. It was in light of this that the Conference of Nigeria's Ambassadors in 1966 stressed the need for the maintenance of good neighbourly relations with all states in general and with Nigeria's immediate neighbours in particular.

However, this was not made easy by French imperialism. From the perspective of the French, a united and prosperous Nigeria would inevitably become a united states of West Africa and would tend to pull former French colonies away from French influence.¹⁵ Nigeria has never lost sight of the French design and the extent of its influence over its former colonies. Before the era of oil politics, Nigeria was conscious of its limited financial capability to offer these countries sufficient assistance to lessen their dependence on France.

In the interim, Nigeria attempted to prove to its immediate neighbours its preparedness to uphold their territorial integrity, provide them with economic assistance, and promote bilateral and sub-regional economic cooperation to ensure joint development of common resources. Nigeria proved this by its role in the Congo crisis and its prompt decision to send troops to help Julius Nyerere suppress mutiny in Tanzania. Nigeria also sought to avoid creating any fear among its weaker neighbours that might encourage them to seek closer ties with the former colonial master. On the problem of boundaries, a source of worry to the newly independent African states, Nigeria assured them that she does not harbour any expansion policy but rather will respect those boundaries in the interest of peace. These assurances lessened the fears of Nigeria's weak and small neighbours. In order to consolidate this position, the Nigerian government dispatched a goodwill parliamentary delegation to Cameroun and other neighbouring states.

To assure African states about its sincerity and seriousness on the matter of non-expansion, African security, and cooperation, the Nigerian government gave a prepared brief to its delegation during the first Pan-African Summit in May, 1963.¹⁶ The objectives were to ensure:

- Sovereign equality of African and Madagascar states, whatever may be the size of their territories, the density of their population, and the value of their possessions;
- Non-interference in the internal affairs of member states;
- Respect for the sovereignty and territorial integrity of each state and for its

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inalienable rights to independence and existence;

- Peaceful and harmonious settlement of all disputes arising among the African and Madagascar states;
- Unqualified condemnation of any subversive activity on the part of the neighbouring states;
- The constant promotion and fostering of all available means of cooperation in the fields of economics, health, nutrition, education, and culture; and
- Dedication to the total emancipation of the dependent territories of Africa.¹⁷

In order to actualize its foreign policy goals, the Nigerian government initiated its own bilateral foreign technical assistance programme in Africa. Among the major beneficiaries were the republics of Cameroun, Chad, Dahomey, Guinea, Kenya, and Malawi. Also enduring was the attempt by the Nigerian government to strengthen its ties with the neighbouring countries through the initiation of various economic cooperation schemes with a view to developing the resources across the borders of several countries as well as improving means of communication and transportation between them. In the early and mid-1960s, there were series of conferences aimed at multinational, regional, and continental economic cooperation. For instance, in November 1966, representatives of ten West African states gathered in Niamey, Niger Republic, under the auspices of the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa. The conference recommended the creation of a West African Economic Community and a permanent regional secretariat to be established at Niamey. Technical committees on regional transport, industrial development, communication, and trade were proposed to work under the direction of the proposed secretariat. President Hammani Diori urged delegates to organise cooperative marketing arrangements for products of the 'complementary' economics of coastal and interior states. Methods, he said, should be established for easier exchange of fruit and timber from coastal countries and cattle from the countries of the interior.¹⁸

This calls for the pooling of resources to encourage bi-lateral and multi-lateral arrangements between West African states. Equally important was the agreement regulating the use of waterways of the Niger River, which was signed in 1963 by Niger, Chad, Dahomey, Ivory Coast, Guinea, Upper Volta, and Cameroun. This led to the formation of the River Niger Commission.¹⁹ The aim of the Commission was to develop close cooperation for the judicious exploitation of the resources. The quest for closer relationships was further achieved and strengthened by the establishment of the Chad

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Basin Commission in May 1964 by Nigeria, Niger, Cameroun, and Chad²⁰. The scheme was to develop the economic potentialities of the Chad Basin and also act as a unifying force for the participating countries. Nigeria maintained a low profile in the meetings and other aspects of the operations of these commissions. The belief was that the neighbouring countries were to be encouraged to come voluntarily to the realisation that their economic and political destiny lies with Nigeria. This conscious effort to strike a benign but cordial disposition vis-à-vis the former French paid off during the civil war.

There were many factors that helped win strong support for Nigeria during its crisis. Because Nigeria's vulnerability was shared by many other newly independent states in Africa, Nigeria's role in organising diplomatic opposition to Nkrumah of Ghana was regarded by some African states as a subversive element and earned the respect and confidence of many African states²¹. The ethnic, sectional, regional, religious, and other related problems that faced Nigeria were also shared by virtually all African countries, especially in West Africa. Chief Anthony Enahoro's comment was quite apt when he warned that "if Nigeria breaks, no one knows how many African countries will survive" (22). This fear of secession was an additional actor that united African states stood behind Nigeria. It was this factor that prompted the OAU's Kinshasa meeting decision to send a consultative mission of six African Heads of State to Nigeria to assure them of the Assembly's desire for territorial integrity, unity, and peace in Nigeria. In Kinshasa, Emperor Haile Selassie of Ethiopia declared that the situation in Nigeria was of concern to them because secessionist tendencies are to be found in almost all African states. President Ahidjo of Cameroun observed that it was the territorial integrity of Nigeria that basically concerned them. President Diori of Dahomey held the same view that the task before them is to end secession in Nigeria and other African states²³.

Two other factors influenced the position of Nigeria's neighbours in the civil war. These were the dependence of landlocked neighbouring countries on Nigeria as an outlet for their export and import commodities and their inability to balance their budget. During the war, both Chad and Niger had problems with their exports because the war disrupted vital export routes to the sea. Both countries were therefore anxious that the Nigerian situation should normalise to enable them have uninterrupted access to the sea ports.

The gravity of the problems of these countries can be better understood when it is realised that both of them and other French-speaking countries in the West African

subregion found it difficult to balance their budgets. Dahomey (Benin Republic) was one of the poorest countries in the region, and by 1966, she had reached the limit of the annual overdraft allowed by the French as early as February of that year. This led to political instability and prevented it from actively involving herself in the Nigerian crisis²⁴. When it eventually did, it played a negative role by allowing the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) to use Cotonou port to airlift materials to the rebel-held areas. As will be shown, Dahomey (Benin) took the decision because of the relatively little assistance it received from the International Committee of the Red Cross. Despite her earlier assurances of support for the federal government as well as its double stance after granting the ICRC permission to use its airport, the paper is persuaded to opine that she did that because of poverty.

Nigeria's Immediate Neighbours and the Civil Wars

The most important roles played by Nigeria's immediate neighbours in the crisis were in the form of boosting the federal government's morale and providing diplomatic support. The degree of enthusiasm displayed by some of Nigeria's neighbours, especially in diplomatic circles, was encouraging. Before the outbreak of the war, Nigeria's immediate neighbours expressed their concern over the degenerating situation in Nigeria. For instance, a Cameroun envoy to Nigeria expressed his desire for the return of normalcy to Nigeria. Other neighbouring countries showed the same concern. The first stage of their formal involvement in the war was the declaration of their position in the conflict in counter to Biafra's claim that a number of countries, including Nigeria's immediate neighbours, had recognised the State of Biafra. In the diplomatic circle, this declaration was a serious blow for the secessionists.

This declaration went a long way in boosting the morale of the federal government, Nigerians, and the federal troops. It also served as a warning to the international community. Throughout the war, Nigeria's immediate neighbours kept reaffirming their support for the federal government, especially in the international fora. For instance, Ngoo, a Cameroun consul, described the Biafra's claims of recognition as false and misleading. He asserted that, as far as his country was concerned, Nigeria was one and there was nothing like the Republic of Biafra. Before then, the Cameroonian President, Ahmadu Ahidjo, said in Yaoundé that there was no question of his country recognising Biafra.²⁵

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In that spirit, the Chadian President, Francois Tombalbaye, assured the Nigerian government that his country would do nothing that might have the unfortunate effect of impairing the corporate existence and territorial integrity of Nigeria. Tombalbaye said, “At this time, your great country comes across the most painful crisis in her life. I come to express in my name personally and in the name of the government of the Republic of Chad our sympathy and encouragement in your increasing efforts to preserve the unity of the great Republic of Nigeria.”²⁶

In his message to General Gowon, President Hammani Diori assured that his government would continue to know no other government than the constitutional government of the Republic of Nigeria, as his government was following with anxiety the events in Nigeria.²⁷ The President of Dahomey (Benin) sent what many considered a belated message of moral support to the federal government of Nigeria. He said it was not competent for any external power to dictate to Nigeria the solution to its conflict. Dr. Emelie Zinsou declared I am against secession any day and in any part of Africa. The political life of Nigeria is not for outsiders to decide. But I wish this year (1969) would bring peace and unity.²⁸

Of all of Nigeria's immediate neighbours, Togo was the most enthusiastic supporter of Nigeria. The essence of this support was that it was consistent and vigorous and lasted from the beginning to the end of the war. Apart from his verbal support at the press conference, President Eyadema frequently visited Lagos and sent high-level delegations, highlighting his country's support for the federal government. In one of his visits to Lagos during the war, President Eyadema told the press that the people of Togo were anxious for the end of the civil war in Nigeria so that the country might take her proper place in fostering the unity of Africa. He said he was visiting Nigeria to discuss with his Nigerian counterpart the wishes of his people to see an end to the rebellion in Nigeria. He also reaffirmed his support for the federal government in his determination to crush the rebellion. The Togolese leader said that “as a result of the brotherly affection which his people had for Nigeria, General Gowon and I have formed a habit of meeting each other always to exchange views on the present conflict in Nigeria”.²⁹

Other neighbouring countries sent messages to the federal government on the outbreak of the civil war. Many of them reaffirmed their support from time to time. Others, in addition to sending messages of support, publicly denounced the rebels. For

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instance, President Sekou Toure of Guinea denounced Ojukwu as the “Tshombe of the Eastern State,” while Col. Juxton of the National Reformation Council of Sierra Leone assured the Nigerian government that his country would do nothing that might have the unfortunate effect of impairing the corporate existence and territorial integrity of Nigeria. He said, “I have followed with keen interest and some concern the events since January 11 and the steps taken by your government to safeguard the territorial integrity of the federation of Nigeria”³⁰. William Tolbert of Liberia also assured the federal government that his government would not recognise the rebels.³¹ Messages of support and reaffirmations of support were also received from other west African countries, such as the Upper Volta, Mali, Senegal, Gabon, and the Central African Republic.³²

The most significant role played by the neighbouring countries in the civil war was in the field of diplomacy, where Nigeria did not do well. From the beginning to the end of the war, it was Nigeria's neighbours that fought the diplomatic war on behalf of the Nigerian government, as Nigeria continued to hold to the idea that the conflict was her internal affairs. Some of the neighbouring countries, seeing the intense diplomatic activities of the rebels, thought differently and, in spite of the discouragement from the federal government, continued to use their initiative, which subsequently led to the Kinshasa Resolution, which ensured total support for the federal government throughout the war.³³

One of the initiators of that resolution was President Ahidjo of Cameroun. He was always at the forefront in the timing of the committee meeting, the drafting of resolutions, attendance, and planning of the strategies designed to present the rebels as intransigent to the wishes of a wider international community. He also ensured that the rebels were not treated at par with the federal government. He and President Mobutu of Zaire were unequivocally opposed to making OAU offices available to the rebels.³⁴

At the time the Consultative Committee met at Niamey, President Ahidjo maintained that the time was ripe to reassert the Committee's support for the federal government and proposed that the members of the Committee come to Yaounde on July 5, 1968, for that purpose. He also tried to debunk the claims of the rebels contributing to a debate at the OAU summit in Algiers. President Ahidjo stated, “Why should they lay down conditions under which they are to receive food for their starving population? What does it matter to the hungry if the food is brought into his house through the back door, the window, or even the roof?”³⁵

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Such contributions helped expose the real motives of the rebels in politicising the issue of relief materials and thereby led to their isolation. During the last meeting of the Committee in Monrovia, Presidents Ahidjo and Mobutu insisted that the communiqué of the meeting should place the blame squarely on the rebels. Accordingly, the Committee appealed to the rebel supporters throughout the world to commit themselves to the goals of Nigerian unity.³⁶

In addition to his active role in the Consultative Committee, President Hammani Diori also concentrated his efforts on persuading governments and organisations not to recognise the rebels but to give maximum support to the federal government. He also provided General Gowon with opportunities to present the case of the Nigerian government by inviting him to Niamey when an African Head of State was visiting Niger. For instance, in November 1968, President Diori invited Gen. Gowon to Niger when the Sudanese President, Sayed Ismail-El-Azhari was visiting the country. There, the Sudanese President pledged his people's support for the federal government. After two months, the Sudanese Ambassador to Nigeria came up with a strong statement reaffirming Sudan's support for the federal government and warned on the consequences of the success of rebellion in Nigeria.³⁷

At the critical stage of the crisis, when members of the Organisation Commone Africaine et Malagache (OCAM), of which he was the chairman, started to make pronouncements in favour of the rebels, and when one of them recognised the rebel regime, President Diori came out forcefully to pledge his support for the federal government of Nigeria. He also paid a special visit to Paris for a discussion with General De-Gaulle in April 1969. There, he succeeded in enlisting the French support for curtailing arms sales to the rebels as a way of forcing them to negotiate with the federal government. Dahomey (Benin) also attempted to play a diplomatic role in the crisis. In August 1967, Dahomey's foreign minister, Emile Zinsou, flew into Lagos to express his willingness to mediate in the conflict. But during this period, the federal government averred that the attempted secession was purely an internal matter. In January 1969, President Zinsou (who had by then become the President of Dahomey), while on a visit to Paris, also took the opportunity of his visit to explain the nature of the Nigerian crisis to General De-Gaulle. He was impressed by the French leader Dahomey's (Benin) concern for the Nigerian crisis.³⁸

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Togo's President Eyadema's diplomatic activity was as courageous as it was useful. Immediately after Gabon's recognition of the rebels, for instance, he held a press conference in Paris to warn that the "Biafran question was threatening African unity" and called for a special meeting of the fourteen nations of OCAM to discuss the Gabonese action. The press conference was as much directed against France as it was meant to discourage other members of OCAM and the French government from recognising the rebels. Although Togo's proposal for a meeting of OCAM did not hold, Eyadema succeeded in arranging a meeting of a smaller *council de l'Entente*. He also continued to play a crucial diplomatic role on behalf of the Federal Government in the form of persuading members of OCAM and other African countries of the futility of recognising the rebels. He also made various attempts to persuade Gen. De-Gaulle on the matter³⁹.

Ghana's diplomatic involvement in the conflict preceded the outbreak of the civil war. In April 1967, a Ghanaian peace mission to Nigeria held a discussion with the federal government on the possibility of settling the crisis without the use of force. Earlier on, a series of diplomatic activities with the encouragement of the British and Americans culminated in the Aburi meeting of January 1967. Although the outcome of the meeting became controversial and appeared to have encouraged the rebels in their efforts to internationalise the conflict, it was a major development in the history of the civil war. A series of other diplomatic activities were carried out by Ghana after the meeting, including sending an invitation to Gowon to come to Accra for a review of the issue and advice on the need to placate the rebels. General Ankrah also sought Gowon's permission to send a high-level fact-finding delegation directly to Ojukwu's headquarters in Enugu. The Ghanaian military leaders also sought to arrange a West African mini-summit to discuss the Nigerian conflict in advance of the OAU meeting in Kinshasa⁴⁰.

Ghana's enthusiasm in the early period of the crisis resulted in strained relations between the two countries. According to the federal officials who met with Ankrah, the general was not happy that Nigeria did not show appreciation for his peace effort. Other neighbouring countries also contributed diplomatically by explaining the reality of the situation to non-African countries, especially Western European countries. Notable among such countries were Chad, Liberia, Senegal, and Mali. Equally important were

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the 'strategic roles' played by most of Nigeria's neighbours during the civil war. This was important because, had the rebels acquired landing facilities from the neighbouring countries early in the war, both the outcome and the duration of the war would have been difficult to determine. This is true because one of the greatest problems of the rebels was the distance over which their planes or other planes bound for their areas had to cover in the course of their flight⁴¹. This not only made transportation costly but also, by making the flights relatively far between, deprived the rebels of the ability to accumulate arms and ammunition as well as other consumer goods to sustain the rebellion. The effect of this on the morale of the rebels and their supporters was significant.

In this respect, the roles played by Cameroun, Togo, Dahomey, and Gabon were significant. For historical and geographical reasons, Cameroun played the most important role in the involvement of the neighbouring countries in the civil war. Cameroun's strategic role came into action even before the outbreak of the civil war. In October 1960, a plane believed to be carrying arms for Eastern Nigeria was forced down at a point 50 miles west of Garwa in Cameroun⁴². This and that of Togo must have taught the rebels some lessons in the danger of flying their planes in the airspace of Nigeria's neighbouring countries. This explains the subsequent use of Portuguese islands by them. Soon after the outbreak of the civil war, the Cameroun government agreed to assist Nigeria by subjecting the rebel enclave to quarantine and by restricting the movement of people and goods across their respective borders. To enforce this policy, President Ahidjo deployed Cameroonian troops along the frontier and sent his secret police into border villages to monitor and intercept unusually large purchases of local and imported goods⁴³.

This restriction involved temporarily suspending the protocol agreement signed in Yaoundé in February 1963 governing the control of the movement of persons and goods between the two countries as soon as Gowon declared a state of emergency throughout Nigeria. This meant that any Nigerian national who wished to travel to Cameroun had to obtain a visa from the Cameroonian Embassy in Lagos, and vice versa. In effect, this provided room for screening of those who travelled between the two countries.

The Cameroun government also warned Col. Ojukwu to check the unlawful behaviour of a group of Igbos who said they were rebel supporters in the Cameroun. The

warning followed the arrest of about 400 rebel supporters in Barmenda in connection with an attempt to murder a Nigerian who the rebel supporters claimed was loyal to the federal government. In a statement issued after the arrest, the Cameroun government stressed that it had nothing to do with the rebel regime and explained that the government only recognised the federal government of Nigeria⁴⁴.

Togo, another close neighbour, refused to allow its airspace to be used by rebel aircraft or planes, which were shuttling between the rebel enclave and the rest of the world. In the early part of 1968, a plane carrying seven tonnes of old Nigerian currency for the rebels was detained in Lome. After several consultations with the federal government, the old currency notes were returned to Nigeria, and the plane was confiscated by the government of Togo.⁴⁵ Nigeria's immediate neighbours, within their limited resources, provided the federal government with material assistance and at least in one known instance, with vital advice on military strategy. The material assistance provided by the neighbouring countries was in the form of accommodation and other facilities during the series of conferences. They hosted these conferences for the purpose of bringing to an end the civil war. In this case, Ghana, Niger, and Cameroun played the most important role. Ghana also provided transport facilities for the rebel leader, Ojukwu, to attend the Aburi meeting.

Nigeria's Post War Diplomacy toward Its Immediate Neighbours

From the above analysis, it is clear that most of the neighbouring countries cooperated fully with the federal government in its attempt to maintain the territorial integrity of Nigeria. For a number of reasons, few African countries either refused to support the federal government nor wavered along the way. However, based on the recommendation of the meeting of Nigerian Ambassadors in 1969, Nigeria commenced its post-war diplomacy by trying to win over those countries whose disposition was inimical to her security interest. This was done through comprehensive policy towards the immediate neighbouring countries. The 1969 Ambassador's meeting recommended stronger bilateral ties with Francophone African countries through financial subvention, sales of power from kanji dam, among others.⁴⁷ All these measures were pursued in post-war years, all geared towards the normalisation of relations with its immediate neighbours. For instance, the federal government took action to improve relations with Dahomey by issuing Nigeria's first interest free loan to another country. Nigeria gave about 3 billion dollars to Dahomey to be used in financing road projects linking the

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Nigerian border with Dahomey's capital. Nigeria also tolerated the cocoa smuggling into Dahomey's until 1975. Nigeria also financed development projects in Dahomey and also acquired major shares in some of her industries. It also entered into a kind of military pact with Dahomey through which some of her service personnel were trained in Nigerian military institutions.⁴⁸

Similar concessions were extended to Niger Republic which was Nigeria's most reliable and trusted neighbour during the civil war years. This brought about the Educational Exchange Programme whereby students from Niger undergo short courses at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and students from Nigeria undergo French courses at the Zunder Ecole Normale. This exchange programme conferred on the two countries advantages as it has been cheaper in terms of time and finance. Nigeria also permitted Niger to benefit from the Kanji Dam power supply on a preferential basis and also purchased shares in Niger prospective industries.⁴⁹

Nigeria's relations with Chad in the post war period were marked by attempt to restore normalcy where Nigeria provided a peace keeping force in Chad. Though in February 1983, Nigeria and Chad had a border conflict, but by May 1983, a peaceful settlement to the dispute was reached between the two countries. Also, Nigeria had spent money to provide relief materials for Chadian refugees. Equally important was the reactivation of the Chad Basin Commission and Niger River Commission which were undertaken and sponsored by Nigeria in the 1970s with the establishment of Chad Basin fund which Nigeria became the principal contributor.⁵⁰

Nigeria made concessions to Cameroun during the civil war and provided economic assistance to Togo, especially in educational exchange programme. The most outstanding effort made by Nigeria on the sub-region was the formation of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the effort that finally led to the treaty of Lagos of May 1975 which gave birth to the sub-regional body. All these efforts were informed by the fact that Nigeria's security interest lies more in cooperation with its immediate neighbours. The civil war experience had exposed Nigeria's true friends and allies though it is true that Nigeria's relations with its immediate neighbours during and after the civil war was full of ups and downs. To maintain a good relationship with its immediate neighbour, Nigeria must pursue and promote closer economic and socio-cultural cooperation that will engender strong fraternal bond and good neighbourliness with its immediate neighbouring countries.

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Conclusion

Diplomacy of good neighbourliness as a foreign policy principle is imported from the sociology of family into the realms of inter-state relations. It denotes a demonstration of friendly and cooperative disposition between states, securing peaceful co-existence and co-prosperity in the international political system. Nigeria's good neighbourliness towards its immediate neighbours (Cameroon, Benin Republic, Chad, Niger, Togo and Equatorial Guinea) is a product of colonial history, cultural affinity, and deliberate policy conceived and implemented within the purview of the concentric circle theory and the principle of national interests. The paper analysed the role played by Nigeria's immediate neighbours in the thirty-months of civil war and highlighted the factors that informed the staunch support Nigeria enjoyed from her neighbours during that period.

Structurally, the paper examined the relationship between Nigeria and her immediate neighbours before and after independence. It also discussed the roles played by Nigeria's post-civil war foreign policy toward its neighbours. Therefore, it is safe to argue that the geopolitics of Nigeria has put on its shoulders, the leadership of the West African sub-region. Given the fact that the size, population, military prowess and economic resources has given Nigeria an edge above her neighbours, it is pertinent to submit that Nigeria should maintain this manifest destiny and play the hegemonic role in the sub-region, especially by taking proactive steps in providing qualitative leadership for co-prosperity with its immediate neighbours as a leeway for peaceful existence.

Bearing in mind that the Nigeria's foreign policy is poignantly described as 'African centred' and concentrically operated, this positive orientation to immediate neighbours is deemed to be in the African tradition of good neighborliness. Pulled from the template of African tradition and implanted with the filial support of African cooperation, Nigeria's foreign policy should continue to demonstrate this positive disposition based on citizen-centred diplomacy.

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